

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO DEVELOPING AESTHETIC THINKING IN FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14808040>

Abstract. *In this article, methodical approaches to the development of aesthetic thinking are described in terms of various tools and methods, the basis of which is the teaching of creative activity and aesthetic concepts, the tools that occupy an important place in the formation of aesthetic thinking: works of art, music, literature, information is provided about aesthetic factors such as painting.*

Keywords: *aesthetic perception, aesthetic taste, moral-aesthetic ideas, technology lessons, critical thinking, aesthetic preferences, cognitive process*

From a scientific-pedagogical perspective, the development of aesthetic thinking in future primary school teachers is a multifaceted problem that requires a comprehensive approach. The relevance of this issue becomes especially evident in the context of modern social problems, including the moral crisis, the loss of ethical guidelines, and the dominance of information flows that affect children's perception of moral and aesthetic norms.

Aesthetic thinking is closely related to moral values. Aesthetic perception, shaped through art, literature, music, and other forms of creativity, should also have ethical aspects in order to contribute to the formation of a well-rounded personality. A methodological approach should be based on the teacher's awareness of the importance of these relationships. This allows the teacher not only to shape aesthetic taste in students but also to develop qualities such as kindness, hard work, and patriotism.

In primary school education, especially in technology lessons, methods that actively involve students in creative activities should be used to form moral-aesthetic ideas. This may include creating works of art, carrying out projects related to labor and creativity. It is important for students to understand the significance of their participation in society from both an aesthetic and moral perspective. One of the main contradictions highlighted in the research is the lack of a systematic approach to work on moral and aesthetic education. There is a need to develop and implement programs that systematically incorporate elements of moral and aesthetic education, especially in technology lessons, where favorable conditions for such education can be created through practical activities.

The use of modern pedagogical technologies is essential for shaping aesthetic thinking: digital resources, game methods, and design tasks. Such methods provide opportunities to develop both aesthetic perception and critical thinking in students, which is crucial for educating responsible and creative citizens.

Teachers should pay attention to the individual characteristics of students, encourage them to express their aesthetic preferences, and develop their ability to reflect on moral and aesthetic issues. This can be achieved through dialogical forms of work, where students discuss and analyze

their own creative works and the works of others in terms of aesthetic and moral content. Engaging students in creative projects allows them to recognize aesthetic perception and understand the moral aspects of their own work. These may include creating decorative items, planning school events, or participating in exhibitions. It is also important to actively use artistic works in both traditional and modern forms (digital images, videos, etc.) to stimulate students' aesthetic perception and emotional responses.

Aesthetic and moral education can be integrated with other subjects (literature, history, music), enabling students not only to master academic material but also to create a unified educational context that develops their moral and aesthetic perception. Thus, the methodological approaches to developing aesthetic thinking in future teachers should account for systematization, the integration of moral and aesthetic values, and the use of active and interactive teaching methods aimed at developing unique thinking and creative attitudes.

The scientific-pedagogical analysis of the methodological approaches to developing aesthetic thinking in future primary school teachers is based on the age characteristics of young schoolchildren and requires considering the key factors influencing their intellectual, emotional, and active development. According to L.S. Vygotsky, children at the primary school age have visual-imaginary thinking, meaning their mental operations are based on visual images. This, in turn, necessitates the use of visual teaching methods, especially in the process of forming aesthetic perception. For example, in technology lessons, it is important to use materials such as drawings, pictures, models, and real objects that stimulate children's aesthetic perception and imagination in developing their sense of beauty and harmony.

As V.S. Mukhina emphasized, the development of imagination and self-reflection also plays an important role. Teachers should encourage students' imagination by giving creative tasks that require changing objects and their images. Such tasks help develop abstract thinking, which is essential for forming aesthetic consciousness.

The emotional sensitivity and dependence of young schoolchildren should be considered as key features in aesthetic education. As N.I. Kiyashchenko pointed out, children's emotional reactions serve as a measure of the effectiveness of aesthetic education. Teachers must create an emotionally rich environment where children can express their aesthetic experiences and understand their significance. This can occur through discussions of art, music, or literature, where children learn to recognize and describe their emotions. As Likhachev noted, aesthetic education also includes developing a sense of the beauty of nature, people, and things. Teachers can incorporate elements of nature and the environment into educational activities to help children develop an emotional appreciation for beauty.

Although reading is the primary activity for young schoolchildren, game remains a significant part of their lives. The game helps develop social and personal qualities such as a sense of justice, leadership, and collectivism. This is very important for aesthetic education because many aesthetic ideals and moral values are formed through game and joint activities. Teachers should encourage students to participate in group creative projects that develop their social skills and aesthetic feelings.

As A.I. Mishchenko noted, voluntary actions are developed in children during the process of completing creative tasks. This allows them to independently evaluate their work and achievements, thereby fostering responsibility for their actions and artistic creations. Teachers can use activities that require students to create artistic works, write essays about beauty, or develop

projects related to aesthetics. This helps develop not only aesthetic thinking but also the ability to express personal aesthetic experiences.

An important aspect of developing aesthetic thinking is the ability of students to analyze their aesthetic desires and discuss them with the teacher and classmates. This can be organized through dialogues and group discussions of art pieces or natural phenomena. As mentioned, the use of visual materials such as pictures, photographs, models, and illustrations is one of the main methods of developing aesthetic consciousness. These tools help shape ideas about beauty and harmony in the world around them. Therefore, methodological approaches to developing aesthetic thinking in future primary school teachers should consider the age characteristics of students, the use of creative tasks and reflection, as well as active use of visual and emotionally rich teaching methods.

The scientific-pedagogical analysis of the methodological approaches to developing aesthetic thinking in future primary school teachers emphasizes the importance of integrating labor and moral-aesthetic education into the educational process. The main focus is on using practical activities related to labor as a tool for developing social virtues such as cooperation, responsibility, and independence, which contribute to the formation of moral and aesthetic norms in young children. Labor is seen not only as a means of creating material and spiritual values but also as a method of personal development. In effective educational activities, especially in technology lessons, children learn practical skills, receive approval for their achievements, and develop creativity and self-expression. This, in turn, shapes their moral-aesthetic ideas about labor and its social significance.

To successfully shape the aesthetic thinking of future teachers, the following educational principles should be considered:

The unity of educational development and formative functions, where the process aims not only to develop cognitive but also aesthetic and moral qualities.

Students' awareness and creativity are essential components of education, helping them develop a conscious attitude towards learning and moral guidelines.

The coherence and unity of the didactic process, where emotional and meaningful components of education go hand in hand.

The principle of appearance, especially important for young schoolchildren, helping to develop aesthetic perception through visual aids and examples.

Oral methods (moral conversations, explanations, stories) aimed at transmitting knowledge and developing children's ability to make moral and aesthetic judgments.

Visual methods (demonstrations, illustrations) that help activate cognitive processes and create conditions for forming aesthetic and moral ideas.

For primary school teachers, it is crucial to begin shaping students' aesthetic perception of the world from an early age. This helps develop their emotional sensitivity, aesthetic taste, and creative self-expression abilities. Pedagogical technologies aimed at developing aesthetic thinking assist in the person's comprehensive development and their ability to perceive beauty in everyday life.

Technology lessons offer unique opportunities for harmonizing practical and aesthetic activities. Independent production activities play a crucial role, since through them, schoolchildren not only develop labor skills but also shape their aesthetic perception of the world around them. Through such activities, they learn to create beautiful and functional objects, which helps develop

their aesthetic senses and understand the harmony in labor and nature. The methodological approaches to developing aesthetic thinking involve various tools and methods, with creativity and teaching aesthetic concepts at the core.

The key tools in shaping aesthetic thinking are the use of aesthetic elements such as artworks, music, literature, and painting. Through these methodological approaches, teachers can not only convey aesthetic knowledge but also stimulate aesthetic feelings, interest, and creativity.

In developing aesthetic thinking in future teachers, reflective and self-assessment methods, creative tasks, and practical activities play a vital role in encouraging students' creative engagement. These methods enable teachers to not only transmit aesthetic knowledge but also foster aesthetic feelings, curiosity, and creativity.

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